

Gerontological Perspectives on Technostress and E-Fatigue Among University of the Philippines Diliman Librarians: Insights on Their Use of Search Engines

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1. Introduction

The increasing integration of digital technologies into library operations has significantly transformed the roles and responsibilities of library professionals. Libraries are increasingly adopting artificial intelligence (AI)-powered search engines to enhance information retrieval. This study investigates the lived experiences of aging librarians as they navigate this evolving digital landscape, with a specific focus on the psychological and physical effects of technostress and e-fatigue. These issues remain underexplored in the context of recent AI adoption and the post-pandemic acceleration of digital transformation. This research addresses a gap in the existing literature, particularly as previous studies on technostress among library staff at the University of the Philippines Diliman were conducted prior to the widespread implementation of AI and the digital shifts prompted by the COVID-19 pandemic. To provide a comprehensive understanding, the study pursued four objectives:

1. To explore the manifestations of technostress and e-fatigue;
2. To assess their impact on psychological well-being, emotional health, and professional performance;
3. To examine coping mechanisms and adaptive strategies; and
4. To understand aging librarians' perceptions and attitudes toward AI integration.

2. Related Literature

Prior research conducted within the University of the Philippines Diliman library system by Bachiller (2001) and Cascolan (2013) examined technostress among library staff. While both studies generally reported low overall levels of technostress, they found correlations between age, frequency of technology use, and stress intensity.

This study situated earlier findings within the broader evolution of search engines in libraries, from basic retrieval systems to sophisticated AI platforms. These advancements have increased the demand for digital literacy among librarians. Technostress is defined as the strain resulting from adapting to technological changes, often manifesting as cognitive overload, anxiety, and decreased job satisfaction. E-fatigue, on the other hand, involves mental exhaustion, reduced concentration, and physical discomfort such as eyestrain due to prolonged digital engagement. From a gerontological perspective, older adults are not inherently resistant to technology but may face unique barriers, including techno-complexity, limited tailored training, and fear of obsolescence.

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3. Methodology

A mixed-methods approach, employing a phenomenological design, guided this investigation. The study population comprised senior librarians (aged 60 years and above) actively engaged in information retrieval tasks using digital or AI-based search tools at the University of the Philippines Diliman. Purposive sampling was utilized to select participants. Data were collected through a semi-structured questionnaire incorporating both closed-ended and open-ended questions. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics while qualitative responses underwent thematic analysis to uncover deeper insights into participants' experiences.

4. Results and Discussions

Findings revealed that technostress was moderately present, with most participants indicating they experienced it “sometimes.” A significant number reported feeling overwhelmed by continuous technological updates, experiencing physical symptoms such as eyestrain and fatigue, and feeling anxious when AI outputs were unclear. Eyestrain emerged as the most common symptom of e-fatigue, followed by headaches. Despite these challenges, most participants found AI tools easy or very easy to use, and the majority agreed that AI improved efficiency and saved time. However, confidence in using AI tools was low, with only two respondents expressing confidence.

Participants demonstrated resilience through various coping strategies, most commonly by taking screen breaks and practicing mindfulness or stress management techniques. Institutional support was highlighted as a key protective factor, with many respondents feeling supported in navigating technological challenges. Perceptions of AI tools were mixed; while many appreciated the efficiency gains, they expressed the need for critical evaluation of AI-generated content. A strong desire for tailored training and ongoing institutional support also emerged.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

In conclusion, this study highlighted the dual impact of AI-powered search engines on aging librarians: while offering significant professional benefits, they also contribute to technostress and e-fatigue. The findings showed the critical need for comprehensive support systems, including age-appropriate training, ergonomic interventions, and wellness initiatives, to foster a more inclusive and sustainable digital work environment for experienced library professionals.

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